

TABLE I—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF MIXED SOLID SOLUTIONS OF Ca, Ba, Cu or Zn AND MEASUREMENT OF LATTICE PARAMETERS

Formulation	Wt %				g-atom ratio (Ca+Ba+Cu/Zn)/P	Lattice parameters		Unit cell volume $\sqrt{3}/2 a^3$
	Ca	Ba	Cu/Zn	P		a	c	
Ca _{1.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	39.89	—	—	18.50	1.666	9.37	6.86	523.12
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Cu _{1.10} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.35	60.10	3.90	10.36	1.667	9.87	7.29	615.02
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.37	55.17	7.50	10.76	1.667	—	—	—
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.51	49.89	11.22	11.20	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{0.95} Ba _{0.07} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.40	48.10	16.37	11.74	1.666	9.55	7.12	562.86
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.04} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.69	35.92	21.90	12.34	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.07} Cu _{1.01} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.89	27.62	27.16	13.03	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{1.04} Ba _{0.11} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	3.07	19.85	33.04	13.71	1.666	9.16	6.71	487.52
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Cu _{1.15} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	3.30	8.63	40.66	14.59	1.667	—	—	—
Ca _{1.05} Cu _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	3.33	—	46.99	15.29	1.667	8.92	6.55	451.34
Cu _{1.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	—	—	51.27	14.99	1.667	8.88	6.58	440.93
Ca _{0.9} Ba _{1.1} Zn _{0.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	23.26	13.31	5.19	16.98	1.667	9.42	6.91	581.02
Ca _{0.71} Ba _{1.05} Zn _{0.95} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	23.35	21.98	5.10	15.26	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{0.95} Ba _{0.05} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	18.76	29.84	5.20	14.22	1.666	9.49	6.96	542.84
Ca _{0.95} Ba _{0.05} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	14.33	38.11	4.72	13.16	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{0.91} Ba _{1.09} Zn _{1.04} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	10.63	44.95	4.50	12.29	1.667	9.81	7.07	589.23
Ca _{0.95} Ba _{0.05} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	7.32	51.03	4.25	11.51	1.666	—	—	—
Ca _{0.95} Ba _{0.05} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	4.74	56.04	3.86	10.88	1.666	9.99	7.19	621.43
Ca _{1.05} Ba _{0.05} Zn _{0.95} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	2.33	60.81	3.44	10.29	1.667	—	—	—
Ba _{0.95} Zn _{1.05} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	—	64.78	3.50	9.76	1.667	10.05	7.45	651.66
Ba _{1.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	—	69.46	—	9.41	1.665	10.19	7.70	692.42

ion Ba^{II} (1.35 Å) and contraction upon the introduction of smaller ion Cu^{II} (0.72 Å) or Zn^{II} (0.74 Å) in place of Ca^{II} ion (0.99 Å) in the apatite lattice. Such contraction of Ca–Ba–CuHA was also evident from the fact that the unit cell volume of the samples (calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constants) decreased with the decrease in the proportion of barium content and consequent increase in the proportion of copper content in Ca–Ba–CuHA. Such dilation of (Ca+Ba+Zn)HA was evident from excellent regularity with which the unit cell volume of the samples increased with increase in the proportion of barium content keeping zinc constant in the mixed solid solutions.

All compositions of solid solution formation were confirmed from the fact that X-ray diffraction findings revealed no reflections except those pertaining to the mixed crystals.

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Chromium(III), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) Complexes with 3-(*m*-Nitrobenzylideneamino)-2-methyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolone

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THE present paper reports the result of our studies on the synthesis and characterisation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Cr^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with the Schiff base derived from 2-methyl-3-amino-4(3*H*)-quinazolone and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of Schiff base: A mixture of 2-methyl-3-amino-4(3*H*)-quinazolone¹ and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol along with a few drops of triethylamine (as catalyst) was refluxed for 4 h. 3-(*m*-Nitrobenzylideneamino)-2-methyl-4(3*H*)-quinazolone precipitated as

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	M.p.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
			M	N	Cl		
MNBQ	Canary yellow	120	—	19.00 (18.18)	—	—	—
Cr(MNBQ) ₂ Cl ₂	Dark yellow	240	6.48 (6.71)	6.84 (7.28)	12.96 (13.75)	8.87	72 ^a
Co(MNBQ) ₂ Cl ₂	Dark brown	260	7.69 (7.90)	6.96 (7.50)	9.25 (9.52)	4.78	20 ^b
Ni(MNBQ) ₂ Cl ₂	Light brown	310	7.80 (7.87)	6.78 (7.50)	9.21 (9.52)	2.98	18 ^b
Cu(MNBQ) ₂ Cl ₂	Dark green	280	8.80 (8.41)	6.88 (7.46)	8.96 (9.45)	1.88	16 ^b
Zn(MNBQ) ₂ Cl ₂	Light yellow	280	14.84 (14.61)	12.11 (12.70)	15.50 (15.97)	—	17 ^b
Cd(MNBQ) ₂ Cl ₂	Dull white	316	22.69 (22.89)	10.90 (11.40)	18.10 (14.48)	—	20 ^b
Hg(MNBQ) ₂ Cl ₂	White	288	33.89 (34.54)	9.14 (6.67)	11.98 (12.26)	—	16 ^b

*MNBQ (Found : C, 61.85, H, 3.62. C₁₀H₁₁O₂N₄ calcd. : C, 62.83 ; H, 3.89%).
 **1 × 10⁻³ M solution in ^aDMF, ^bCCl₄.

a light yellow solid in the hot solution and was filtered and recrystallised from tetrahydrofuran.

Preparation of complexes : The complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of ethanolic solutions of the respective metal chloride and tetrahydrofuran solution of the ligand. For Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes, the refluxing time was 10 h and the metal ligand ratio 1 : 2, while for the rest, time was 7 h and the ratio 1 : 1. pH was maintained at ≈6–7 by dropwise addition of sodium acetate solution. The resulting complexes were filtered, washed with alcohol and ether and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The Cr^{III} complex was soluble in DMF and the others were soluble in CCl₄. ¹H nmr spectra of the ligand and the complexes in DMSO were recorded on a EM-390 spectrometer at R.S.I.C., Madras.

Results and Discussion

Analytical and physical data are given in Table 1. The Cr^{III} complex is a 1 : 1 electrolyte while the others are non-ionic as indicated from their molar conductance values.

The infrared spectra of the free ligand show two characteristic bands at 1 680 (C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N)³. The lower shifts of $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ bands by about 20 and 25 cm⁻¹, respectively, in all the complexes show coordination through amido oxygen⁴ and azomethine nitrogen⁴. The coordination through oxygen of C=O and nitrogen of C=N in all the complexes have been further confirmed by the appearance of ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} bands at 540–570 and 460–480 cm⁻¹, respectively⁶. The ir spectra of all the complexes show an additional band at ~275 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ν_{M-Cl} ⁶.

The visible spectra of the Cr^{III} complex exhibits three bands at 17 300 (ν_1), 23 100 (ν_2) and

3 600 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) which may be assigned to the transitions ⁴A_{2g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F), ⁴A_{2g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(F) and ⁴A_{2g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P), respectively. The ν_1 and ν_2 bands are intense, but ν_3 appears as shoulder. The crystal field parameters ν_3/ν_1 , Dq/B, 10Dq, B and β values have been found to be 1.33, 2.56, 17024 cm⁻¹, 665 cm⁻¹ and 0.64, respectively. The lowering in the value of B from the free-ion value for Cr^{III} (1 030 cm⁻¹) suggests 35.45% covalent nature of bonding. The μ_{eff} value of the Cr^{III} complex is also indicative of its octahedral geometry. These values are in good agreement with the reported values for octahedral complexes⁷ of Cr^{III}. The visible absorption spectra of the Co^{II} complex show three band at 9 000, 18 900 and 22 150 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to transitions ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν_1), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν_2) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν_3), respectively. The crystal field parameters ν_3/ν_1 , Dq/B, 10Dq, B and β have been found to be 2.01, 1.05, 10 500 cm⁻¹, 1 000 cm⁻¹ and 0.89, respectively. The μ_{eff} value (4.78 B.M.) of the Co^{II} complex is also indicative of its octahedral geometry. These values are in close accordance with the spin-free octahedral geometry of Co^{II} complex⁸. The lowering in the value of B (10.71%) from the free-ion value for Co^{II} (1 120 cm⁻¹) suggests covalent nature of bonding. The low value of B is attributed to the high intensity of the absorption band. The visible absorption spectra of the Ni^{II} complex show three peaks at 8 560, 13 690 and 25 300 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to the transitions ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F) (ν_1), ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(F) (ν_2) and ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(P) (ν_3), respectively. The crystal field parameter, ν_3/ν_1 , Dq/B, 10Dq, B and β values have been found to be 1.5, 1.1, 9 590.9 cm⁻¹, 871.9 cm⁻¹ and 0.83%. Decrease in the Racah parameter value after coordination has been found to be 16.25. The μ_{eff} value of the Ni^{II} complex (2.28 B.M.) is also indicative of its octahedral geometry. These values are in close accordance with the reported values⁹ for an octahedral Ni^{II} complex. The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

The ^1H nmr spectra of the ligand show signals at δ 7.1–9.0 due to aromatic protons¹⁰, at δ 2.46 due to methyl protons, and singlet at δ 8.3–8.6 due to $-\text{CH}=\text{N}$ moiety. In the complexes of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} the latter signal undergoes a downward shift at δ 8.8–9.1 indicating the participation of azomethine nitrogen in the complexes¹¹.

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Stability Constants of Ternary Metal(II)/2,2'-Dipyridylamine/Amino Acidate Complexes of Nickel, Zinc and Cadmium

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THE present paper reports the stability constants of ternary MAL complexes, where, $\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ; $\text{A} = 2,2'$ -dipyridylamine and $\text{L} = \text{anion}$

of glycine, α -alanine, leucine, isoleucine, valine, serine, threonine, methionine and aspartic acid determined by modified pH metric method following Irving–Rossotti pH-titration technique^{1,2}.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A. R. grade. Solutions for the equilibrium study were prepared in conductivity water. Free perchloric acid and metal perchlorate solutions were standardised by acid-base³ and complexometric⁴ methods. The experimental set-up and calculations were employed as described by Mavani *et al.*⁵. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 *M* using 1 *M* sodium perchlorate. A Elico LI-10 T pH meter was employed for pH measurements. Potentiometric titrations were carried out at 27° using 0.2 *M* NaOH.

The formation constants were calculated by the literature methods⁶. Precise values of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ (Table 1) were determined by the method of averages⁶, here L stands for amino acid anions.

Results and Discussion

The $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ values are found to be much higher than $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{ML}}$, and are only slightly lower than $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$. The order of formation constants for the mixed ligand chelates is the same as that for the binary ML complexes⁷. The $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ values are in the order, glycine $\gg$ α -alanine $\approx$ leucine $\gg$ isoleucine $>$ valine, serine $\approx$ threonine $\approx$ methionine $<$ aspartic acid for the ligands L. The sequence may be explained⁷ in terms of the basicities and structures of the secondary ligands L. Higher values of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ originate from the π -acidic nature of 2,2'-dipyridylamine, besides the $\text{N} \rightarrow \text{M}(\text{II})$ σ -bonding, there exists strong $\text{M}(\text{II}) \rightarrow \text{N}$ π -interaction. As a result the electronegativity of the $\text{M}(\text{II})$ ion in $[\text{M}(2,2'\text{-dipyridylamine})]^{2+}$ complex is not significantly different than that of $[\text{M}(\text{aq})_n]^{2+}$ ion^{8,9}.

TABLE 1—MIXED LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS* OF METAL(II)/2,2'-DIPYRIDYLAMINE AMINO ACIDATE COMPLEXES

Amino acid ligand	Temp. = 27°, Ionic strength = 0.2 <i>M</i> (NaClO_4)								
	$\log K_{\text{NIL}}^{\text{NI}}$	$\log K_{\text{NIL}_2}^{\text{NIL}}$	$\log K_{\text{NIAL}}^{\text{NIA}}$	$\log K_{\text{ZnL}}^{\text{Zn}}$	$\log K_{\text{ZnL}_2}^{\text{ZnL}}$	$\log K_{\text{ZnAL}}^{\text{ZnA}}$	$\log K_{\text{CdL}}^{\text{Cd}}$	$\log K_{\text{CdL}_2}^{\text{CdL}}$	$\log K_{\text{CdAL}}^{\text{CdA}}$
Glycine	5.90	5.05	5.23	5.22	4.37	5.08	4.24	3.69	4.20
α -Alanine	5.55	4.53	4.93	5.17	4.10	4.92	4.27	3.46	4.15
Leucine	5.54	4.55	5.24	4.74	4.36	4.69	4.92	3.56	4.18
Isoleucine	5.43	4.49	4.95	4.88	4.33	4.81	3.91	3.37	3.96
Valine	5.48	4.42	4.90	4.74	4.24	4.63	3.91	3.22	3.88
Serine	5.69	4.76	5.21	5.06	4.11	4.71	3.95	3.30	3.76
Threonine	5.96	4.93	5.35	5.16	4.19	4.85	4.02	3.20	3.72
Methionine	5.60	4.81	5.38	4.69	3.96	4.54	4.30	4.04	3.85
Aspartic acid	7.12	5.32	6.75	5.74	4.09	5.52	4.53	3.50	4.61

* Limits of error: $\pm 0.01 - 0.08$ in log scales.